

STRESS ANALYSIS AND DAMAGE DETECTION IN A STEPPED COMPOSITE PLATE

Wei Tong

Department of Engineering Mechanics
University of Nebraska-Lincoln
Lincoln, Nebraska 68588-0347 U.S.A.

Wolfgang G. Knauss

Graduate Aeronautical Laboratories
California Institute of technology
Pasadena, California 91125 U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

A three dimensional finite element stress analysis is carried out for a stepped composite plate. The aim of the numerical analysis is to interpret the experimental observation of the failure process during a bending test of the composite plate. Effects of the geometry discontinuities (the free-edge and the step) as well as the laminate lay-up and stacking sequence on stress concentration and potential damage initiation sites of the stepped plate are investigated. The role of the detailed geometry of the step (sharp and rounded) is also examined.

I. INTRODUCTION

Co-cured, stringer-reinforced composite plates and shells have proven themselves to be a very efficient means of constructing parts such as aircraft wings and fuselage skins. When the plates or shells are subjected to buckling loads, they often maintain considerable strength well into the post-buckling regime [1-2]. Ultimate failure of these plates and shells is largely controlled by the damage initiation and growth that lead to the local failure of the stiffener/skin intersection. To predict and design against this type of failure, it is important to assess stresses and to identify the damage mechanism and process at the stiffener/skin interface.

Because the geometric discontinuity in the thickness of the composite plate (i.e., the step or reentrant corner), the stresses can become unbounded. The failure at the stiffener/skin intersection is regarded as a process controlled by the severity of the stress singularity at the vicinity of the step [3-5], similar to stress intensity factors in fracture mechanics. An analytic solution has been obtained for a corner in an isotropic, homogeneous, infinite plate [6]. Solutions for a reentrant corner with an orthotropic material have largely been obtained through numerical calculations. The stress singularity at the corner was analyzed by a combination of global and local finite ele-

ment calculations and an elastic eigenvalue expansion of the stress functions [3-4]. Three dimensional effects was later examined to a certain degree by a plane-coupled strain finite element formulation [5]. The effects of the stacking sequence on the stress singularity were also examined for up to 23 different lay-ups [5].

Recently, an experimental investigation of the failure of a stepped composite plate was carried out to detect the damage initiation and growth by *in-situ* microscopic inspection of the specimen edges [7]. The experimental evidence indicates that the damage initiation does not always occur on the plate-stringer interface; it was discovered that in some lay-ups, damage initiates at a distance of over one lamina thickness away from the step. It raises the question about the validity of the failure criterion based on exclusively a computed stress singularity at the step of the composite plate. Because the specimen geometry used in the experiments is relatively small in width, effects of free edges on the damage initiation and growth may be critical [8-9]. A three dimensional finite element analysis is thus carried out to examine the effects of the geometric discontinuities of both the free edge and the step on interlaminar stresses and to assess the damage initiation process in the stepped composite plates. In this paper, the finite element models of the specimen geometry and loading conditions used in the experiments are presented in Section II. The results of the three-dimensional finite element analysis are discussed in Section III. Some results from the experimental observation are summarized in Section III for comparison as well. Some conclusions drawn from this study are given in Section IV.

II. 3D FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

A three-dimensional finite element analysis is used to assess the stress states at both the free edge and the step. The analysis is linear in nature and formulated via a displacement-based approach. Fig. 1 shows the specimen geometry used in the experimental investigation [7]. Both the plate and the stringer are made of 8-ply AS4/3502 carbon-fiber-reinforced epoxy. Each ply is measured to be 0.125 mm thick (standard tape thickness) which results a thickness of 1 mm for both the plate and the stringer. The carbon fiber is estimated to be 5 μm and smaller in diameter. Each ply or individual laminate of the composite plate is modelled as a homogenous, transversely orthotropic, linear elastic material. A total four different lay-ups are considered in the current analysis: (1) plate-[90,+45,0,-45]s and stringer-[90,+45,0,-45]s; (2) plate-[+45,0,-45,90]s and stringer-[+45,0,-45,90]s; (3) plate-[90,0,-45,+45]s and stringer-[0,-45,+45,90]s; (4) plate-[0,-45,90,+45]s and stringer-[90,+45,0,-45]s. Each ply listed in the order is laid up from bottom to top in Fig. 1. The stepped composite plate is fully clamped at the thick end A and loaded at the thin end B with a downward force. Materials constants used for the numerical analysis are:

$$E_{11}=138\text{E}+3 \text{ MPa (20.0E}+6 \text{ psi)}, E_{22} = E_{33}=14.5\text{E}+3 \text{ MPa (2.1E}+6 \text{ psi)}, \\ G_{12} = G_{13} = G_{23} = 5.86 \text{ MPa (0.85E}+6 \text{ psi)}, \nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = \nu_{23}=0.21.$$

The coordinate system and naming convention is given in Fig. 2 for the finite element modeling and subsequent discussions. Three-dimensional brick elements (8- or 20-node 3D isoparametric elements) are used to mesh the entire stepped composite plate; a very coarse mesh of the plate is shown in Fig. 3. In order to capture the details of the stress variation near the free edge and the step, a nonuniform meshing scheme is used in the final calculation. An example of the actual mesh is shown in Fig. 4 around the step at the negative side of the free edge (the thickness of the plate is not proportionally scaled). Interface plies (one on the plate side and one on the stringer side) are modeled by four elements through their thickness. The plies next to the interface plies are modeled by two elements through their thickness. Rest of the plies in both the plate and the stringer are modeled by a single element along their thickness. The mesh has a mirror symmetry

about the xz -plane at $y=0$. Furthermore, effects of the filled corner at the step on the stresses are examined by modeling the step with two different geometries: sharp and rounded corners (see Fig. 5).

To verify the current implementation of the material models and accuracy of the finite element analysis (non-uniform meshing), free-edge effect in a symmetric, angle ply (45/-45) laminate [10] is studied at first. The laminate has length $2L$, width $2W$, and thickness $2H$, with $L=10W$ and $W=4H$. Each ply of the laminate is of equal thickness h , and is assumed as a homogeneous, orthotropic material. The laminate is subjected to axial displacements on the ends. The mesh used is shown in Fig. 6. The distribution of transverse normal stress through the thickness of the laminate at the free edge is shown in Fig. 7. The distribution of transverse shear stress across the width of the laminate is shown in Fig. 8. These results agree well with those obtained by Robbins and Reddy [10]

In the following section, results of the 3D finite element analysis of a stepped composite plate will be presented and compared with some microscopic experimental observation of the damage initiation process.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Summary of the Experimental Observation

The primary means of damage detection was *in-situ* microscopic inspection of the specimen edges. These observations were supplemented by penetrant-dye inspection, microscopic inspection of the plate face, and ultrasonic C-scanning of specimens which were unloaded prior to catastrophic failure [7]. According to the observation, the ply that seems to play the most important role in determining failure is the plate interface ply. If this ply has a low axial failure stress (90° orientation), it is likely that it will fail before the stress on the stringer-plate interface becomes large enough to cause failure by the step. However, if this ply is relatively strong, it is likely that the stress on the stringer-plate interface will lead to failure. Similarly, the plies below the plate interface ply influence the damage progress through their contribution to the plate's bending strength and stiffness. For specimens tested, the failure-initiation loads (from 0.4 N.m to 1.3 N.m) and catastrophic loads (from 1.1 N.m to 1.9 N.m) increases as the plate's bending stiffness increases.

As an example, one of the series of micrographs detailing the initial damage development of a stepped composite plate at the negative edge is shown in Fig. 9. The lay-up of the specimen is Case 1, i.e., plate-[90,+45,0,-45,-45,0,+45,90] and stringer-[90,+45,0,-45,-45,0,+45,90]. The schematic of the damage process observed at both the positive and negative edges is shown in Fig. 10 and 11. The numbers in both figures denote the occurring sequence of failure events. For this particular lay-up, the damage initiates with cracking in the plate interface ply (a 90° ply) near the step (about one ply thickness away) and propagates through the next plate ply (a $+45^\circ$ ply). The delamination occurs at the interface between the $+45^\circ$ ply and the 0° ply in the plate, *not at the stringer-plate interface*.

Stress Distribution Around the Step

Because the damage initiation often occurs in the plate interface ply in the stepped composite specimens, the stress distribution at the stringer-plate interface ($z=0$) for the sharp corner case is given, see Figs. 12-14. Both variations of stresses across the step (a) and over the width of the

specimen (b) are plotted. The stress variations along the center line ($y=0$), the positive edge ($y/W=+0.993$) and the negative edge ($y/W=-0.993$) are plotted in solid, dot-dashed, and short-long dashed lines respectively in Figs. 12(a), 13(a), and 14(a). Here $2W=25.4$ mm (1 in).

The interlaminar stress variations from the negative edge ($y/W=-1$) to the positive edge ($y/W=+1$) at the step ($x=0$), near the step ($x=-0.35$ mm) and away from the step ($x=-15$ mm) are plotted in solid, dashed, and dot-dashed lines respectively in Figs. 12 (b) and 13(b). In Fig. 14(b), variations of the transverse normal stress σ_x at the step ($x=0$), near the step in the stiffened side ($x=-0.35$ mm), and near the step in the unstiffened side ($x=+0.22$ mm) are plotted in solid, dashed, and dotted lines respectively. The concentration of interlaminar normal and shear stresses is severe near the step. The results of interlaminar stresses at the center (solid lines) in Fig. 12(a) and Fig. 13(a) show the same characteristic as in [3]. At the free edges, however, the magnitude of the normal peeling stress σ_z is reduced significantly. The maximum normal and shear stresses at the stiffener-plate interface is at the step and away from the negative edge about 1/8 of the width ($y/W=-0.75$).

As shown in Fig. 14(a), the transverse normal stress σ_x in the plate interface ply is nominally zero on the stiffened side away from the step (say $x < -5$ mm). The stress intensifies dramatically as approaching the step. The plate interface ply is subjected to a large transverse normal stress in tension on the unstiffened side away from the step (say $x = +5$ mm or larger). The free edge has a lesser effect on the transverse normal stress, see Fig. 14(b). Near both the positive and negative edges, the transverse normal stress remains much higher than the interlaminar normal stress.

At the micromechanics level, the damage can initiate due to the interply delamination, fiber breakage, and matrix cracking in the neat resin core [11-14]. The 3D finite element calculations indicate that for certain lay-ups such as Case 1 in this study the transverse normal stress could overtake the interlaminar stresses as the dominant cause in damaging the stepped composite plate near the step, which is consistent with the experimental observation. Beside the free edge effects in reducing the magnitude of interlaminar stresses, the less-than-sharp corner (Fig. 9 and Fig. 5b) at the step also lessens the interlaminar stress concentration while the transverse normal stress is still very high near the end of rounded corner on the unstiffened side, approximately one ply thickness away from the step [14].

IV. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The magnitude of the interlaminar stress concentration at the stringer-plate intersection in a stepped composite plate is reduced by the free edge and by a less-than-sharp corner geometry of the step. For lay-ups in which there is a ply near the interface with a low axial failure stress (for example 90° and 45° orientations, matrix cracking will occur prior to delamination. A nonlinear finite element analysis is required to predict the subsequent damage modes and progress in the composite specimen. Experimentally, bending tests of the stepped composite plates will be refined with a better loading control and a high resolution digital image acquisition system for the in-situ microscopic inspection of specimen edges. Local displacement fields around the step will be computed using a digital image correlation of microimages of composite specimens for verification of 3D finite element calculations. Hygrothermal effects on the damage initiation and progress will be investigated by conducting the experiments in an environmental chamber. The combined experimental and computational investigation of the failure of a stepped composite plate will further our understanding of damage micromechanics of carbon-fiber-reinforced epoxy composites.

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Fig. 1 Specimen geometry.

Fig. 2 Coordinate system and naming convention.

Fig. 3 A coarse mesh for the specimen.

Fig. 4 A detailed view of the mesh around the step on the negative edge.

(a) sharp corner

(b) rounded corner

Fig. 5 A detailed view of the step at the negative edge

Fig. 6 Nonuniform mesh used for the symmetric angle ply laminate.

Fig. 7. Distribution of transverse normal stress through the thickness of the laminate at the free edge.

Fig. 8. Distribution of transverse shear stress across the width of the laminate.

Fig. 9 Micrograph taken on the negative edge.

Fig. 10. Damage development on the positive edge.

Fig. 11. Damage development on the negative edge.

Fig. 12. Variations of the interlaminar peeling stress around the step.

Fig. 13 Variations of the interlaminar shear stress around the step.

Fig. 14. Variations of the transverse normal stress around the step.